

Towards the automation of aircraft ground movement operations with towbarless robotic tractors

Almudena Buelta, Alberto Olivares, Ernesto Staffetti

Universidad Rey Juan Carlos

Fuenlabrada, Madrid, Spain

almudenajose.buelta@urjc.es, alberto.olivares@urjc.es, ernesto.staffetti@urjc.es

Abstract—Currently, aircraft ground movement operations are performed using tractors driven by humans. When performing these operations, which, due to the size of the aircraft and the presence of obstacles, are generally rather complex, the situational awareness of the driver is limited. This fact poses a potential risk, which could be mitigated by using robotic tractors. Therefore, this paper focuses on the automation of these operations, specifically on the planning and control of aircraft ground movement operations with towbarless robotic tractors. The tractor-aircraft system is modeled as a car-like mobile robot with an off-hooked trailer. A dynamic model of the tractor-aircraft system is employed. Assuming that the positions of the obstacles are known, the primary focus of this research is planning collision-free paths to steer the aircraft from the initial to the final position. This problem is formulated as an optimal control problem, which is solved using a pseudospectral knotting numerical method. Since the tractor-aircraft system moves in reverse during some ground movement operations, such as pushback maneuvers, the issue of jackknifing is taken into account. Consequently, this paper also tackles the problem of tracking the planned trajectory while averting jackknifing. The trajectory tracking problem is solved using a Jacobian linearization of the offset dynamics about the planned trajectory. The numerical results demonstrate the effectiveness of the proposed methods.

Index Terms—Tractor-trailer systems, trajectory planning, trajectory tracking, numerical optimal control

I. INTRODUCTION

Airport ground operations encompass a wide range of activities within airport management, such as aircraft movement, baggage handling, aircraft refueling, and general ramp services. Increasing safety and efficiency in these operations is crucial for enhancing overall airport performance.

Aircraft movement operations include taxiing, apron maneuvering, which includes pushback, and towing. Taxiing is the process of guiding an aircraft on the ground from one location to another, such as from the parking position to the runway for takeoff or from the runway to the gate after landing. Currently, taxiing movements are executed using aircraft engines as well as apron forward maneuvers, while pushback maneuvers are executed using specialized equipment known as pushback tractors or tugs. Aircraft pushback is typically managed by pilots, air traffic controllers, and a specialized team, which usually includes a headset person, a tractor driver, two wing walkers, and a tail walker. In some cases, aircraft may be

towed by tractors to and from different locations on the airport grounds, e.g., parking areas or maintenance facilities.

In [1], the International Civil Aviation Organization gave the specifications of the Advanced Surface Movement Guidance & Control System (A-SMGCS), a system providing routing, guidance, and surveillance for the control of aircraft and vehicles on the ground at airports. The A-SMGCS Target Level of Safety is 1×10^{-8} collisions per operation involving aircraft on the ground. However, the sector of aircraft ground movement operations has experienced minimal evolution towards automation over the past few decades, as tractors have remained relatively unaffected by technological progress to improve safety. Innovative systems for aircraft ground movement operations are limited to electrically powered remote controlled tractors for taxiing and pushback operations. An international consortium led by Israel Aerospace Industries¹ is developing towbarless tractors named TaxiBot, designed for towing the aircraft during the taxi-out phase and partially in the taxi-in phase, which are operated by pilots via the standard aircraft controls. The Mototok company² produces remotely controlled aircraft tugs, which are compact towbarless tractors designed for pushback operated by ground personnel from a remote location via a handheld control unit. The WheelTug company³ produces an in-wheel electric taxiing system that enables commercial aircraft to move forward and backwards without using the jet engines or needing a tractor. The system uses twin electric motors installed in the rims of the wheels of the nose landing gear of the aircraft, which are powered by the aircraft's auxiliary power unit and operated by pilots via the standard aircraft controls.

Aircraft ground damage is a significant problem that compromises the safety of both passengers and personnel and has a significant impact on the costs of airlines, being towbarless tractors the ground service equipment of the technical servicing that causes most damage to aircraft [2]. These facts demonstrate that it is necessary to increase the level of automation in airport ground operations and, in particular, in aircraft movement operations. Therefore, this paper focuses on

¹<https://taxibot-international.com>

²<https://www.mototok.com>

³<https://www.wheeltug.com>

the automation of these operations, specifically on the problem of planning and tracking aircraft movement operations with towbarless robotic tractors. Assuming that the positions of the obstacles are known, the primary focus of this research is on designing collision-free paths to guide the tractor-aircraft system from the initial to the final position. The tractor is modeled as a car-like mobile robot and, since in towbarless tractors the nose gear of the aircraft is lifted and its wheels are clamped in a cradle within the tractor, the aircraft is regarded as an off-hooked trailer. A dynamic model of the tractor-aircraft system is employed [3] because it allows trajectories to be accurately planned, taking into account the inertial parameters of the subsystems, tractor specifications, such as the maximum drawbar pull for starting from rest and the continuous or rated drawbar pull at which the tractor can work for longer periods, and the forces that arise in the interaction of the wheels of the tractor-aircraft system with the ground, such as the rolling resistance. This problem is formulated as an optimal control problem and solved using a pseudospectral knotting numerical method [4].

The first objective of the paper is to establish whether this optimal control technique is able to plan trajectories for complex maneuvers of the dynamic model of the tractor-aircraft system, such as pushback, repositioning from one parking zone to another, or 180° turn maneuvers. Since the tractor-aircraft system moves in reverse during some maneuvers, the issue of jackknifing, caused by unstable zero dynamics [5], is also taken into account. Consequently, the second objective of the paper is devising a tracking method to follow the planned trajectory while averting jackknifing.

The main contributions of this paper are an accurate dynamic model of the tractor-aircraft system, a trajectory planning method based on optimal control, and a control technique to track the planned trajectory capable of avoiding jackknifing.

II. METHODOLOGY

A. Model of the system

The dynamic model of the tractor-trailer system proposed in [3] has been employed. Let $q = [x \ y \ \theta \ \varphi_1]^T$ be the configuration vector of the tractor-trailer system, where x and y are the coordinates of the middle point of the rear axle of the tractor in the frame of the workspace, and θ and φ_1 are defined in Fig. 1. Let δ be the angle of the steering wheels of the tractor with respect to its longitudinal axis. The lengths of the bodies of the tractor-trailer system are $L_i = a_i + b_i, i = 1, 2$. The dimensional parameters $a_i, b_i, i = 1, 2$, and c_1 of the system are defined in Fig. 1, where point G_i is the center of mass of body $i, i = 1, 2$. Let $\mu_i = [v_{u_i} \ v_{w_i} \ \Omega_i]^T, i = 1, 2$, be the velocity of body i , where v_{u_i} and v_{w_i} are the components of the velocity of the center of mass G_i along the axes u_i and w_i , respectively, and Ω_i is the angular velocity of the body i .

The complete dynamical model of the tractor-trailer system is

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{\alpha} &= D^{-1}(q, \delta) \left(- \left(C_1(q, \delta, \alpha) + C_2(q, \delta) \dot{\delta} \right) \alpha \right. \\ &\quad \left. + J^T(q, \delta) \omega_a(\delta, F_u) \right), \\ \dot{q} &= J_{nh}(q, \delta) \alpha, \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where $\alpha = v_{u_1}$ is the component of the velocity of the center of mass of the tractor along the axis u_1 and $F_u = [F_{u_1} \ F_{u_2} \ \dots \ F_{u_6}]^T$, in which $F_{u_j}, j = 1, 2, \dots, 6$, are the longitudinal forces applied to the 6 wheels. The state vector of the tractor-trailer system is $X = [x \ y \ \theta \ \varphi_1 \ \delta \ \alpha]^T$, in which distances are expressed in m, angles in rad, and the speed α in m/s. The rolling resistance [6], which always acts in the opposite direction to the motion, has been included in the model. Assuming that the propulsion is applied to the 4 wheels of the tractor, $F_{u_j}, j = 1, 2, \dots, 4$, are the propulsion control inputs, whereas $F_s = \dot{\delta}$ is the steering control input. The other elements of the dynamic model (1) of the tractor-trailer system are defined in [3].

B. Trajectory planning

The trajectory planning problem has been formulated as an optimal control problem and solved using the pseudospectral knotting method [4], which is a generalization and improvement of the standard pseudospectral method for optimal control that provides an efficient way to handle nonsmooth controls. The optimal control problem is stated as follows: Consider the dynamic system (1), whose state and control variables are, in general, subject to a set of algebraic equality and inequality constraints, for instance on the speed α or on the φ_1 and δ angles. Given an initial and a final state, find the control inputs and the corresponding trajectory that steer the system between these two states, fulfilling the differential constraints (1) and the algebraic constraints, minimizing an objective functional. The duration of the maneuver may be fixed in advance or left free.

C. Trajectory tracking

The trajectory tracking method proposed in [7] has been employed, which is able to avoid jackknifing when tracking the planned trajectory in reverse motion. Given the actual and desired values of the vehicle speed, heading, and position relative to the desired path, the path-tracking controller provides the control inputs that bring to zero the difference between the actual and desired values. A path-tracking assignment is the combination of a path in the configuration space and a profile of the linear and angular velocities at which the path is to be followed. A path-tracking assignment is admissible if it is compatible with the dynamic model of the tractor-trailer system. Given a state of the tractor-trailer system and the desired state that corresponds to an admissible path-tracking assignment, the path tracking offsets are defined and the offset dynamics about the planned trajectory is calculated and linearized. A time-varying linear system is obtained, which can be controlled using standard control techniques. A linear quadratic regulator is employed for this purpose. More details on this trajectory tracking method can be found in [7].

Fig. 1. The tractor-aircraft system.

III. RESULTS

In this section, the results of two numerical experiments will be outlined. In these experiments a pushback and a 180° turn maneuver have been planned and the resulting trajectories have been tracked. In the optimal control problem, the objective functional to be minimized is a combination of the duration of the maneuver and the energy consumption.

A. Pushback maneuver

The initial and final states of the system are $X_I = [0 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0]^T$ and $X_F = [-80 \ 0 \ -\frac{\pi}{2} \ 0 \ 0 \ 0]^T$, respectively. In planning this maneuver, algebraic inequality constraints on the minimum clearance of the tractor-aircraft system from the airport terminal have been included. The resulting path of the tractor-aircraft system is represented in Fig. 2. The duration of this maneuver is 40.9096 s. The computation time to find this solution on a standard laptop computer using 50 nodes in the pseudospectral knotting method was 65.1887 s.

B. 180° turn on runway turn pad maneuver

The initial and final states of the system are $X_I = [0 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0]^T$ and $X_F = [0 \ -10 \ \pi \ 0 \ 0 \ 0]^T$, respectively. In planning this maneuver, algebraic inequality constraints on the minimum distance of the wheels of the tractor-aircraft system from the boundary of the turn pad have been included. The resulting path of the tractor-aircraft system is represented in Fig. 3. The duration of this maneuver is 47.1659 s. The computation time to find this solution on a standard laptop computer using 50 nodes in the pseudospectral knotting method was 80.3684 s.

IV. DISCUSSION

The solutions of two complex trajectory planning problems for the tractor-aircraft system have been obtained, in which stringent constraints have been introduced. In the pushback maneuver in Experiment A, the y coordinates of the initial

and final states coincide, resulting in a maneuver in which the tractor-aircraft system is not allowed to move very far backward in the y direction as usual in pushback maneuvers. In the 180° turn maneuver in Experiment B, the difference between the y coordinates of the initial and final states is 10 m. Additionally, minimum distance constraints between the wheels of the tractor trailer system and the boundary of the turn pad have been introduced, resulting in a very complex maneuver in which the tractor-aircraft system moves first forward and then backward.

V. CONCLUSION

The results of the numerical experiments confirm that the pseudospectral knotting method employed to solve the optimal control problem is able to plan complex maneuvers in computation times compatible with operational use in an airport and that the path tracking method based on Jacobian linearization of the offset dynamics about the planned trajectory is able to track the planned trajectories avoiding jackknifing.

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Fig. 2. Experiment A: Pushback maneuver. Path of the tractor-aircraft system. The black vertical line segment represents the terminal building. The tracks of the wheels of the main and the nose landing gears of the aircraft are represented in blue and yellow, respectively. The tracks of the front and rear wheels of the tractor are represented in green and red, respectively.

Fig. 3. Experiment B: 180° turn on runway turn pad maneuver. Path of the tractor-aircraft system. The black line segments represent the boundary of the turn pad. The tracks of the wheels of the main and the nose landing gears of the aircraft are represented in blue and yellow, respectively. The tracks of the front and rear wheels of the tractor are represented in green and red, respectively.